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Review Article

Formulation and Evaluation of a Peel-Off Face Mask Using Butterfly Pea Flower (*Clitoria ternatea* Linn.) Extract

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ABSTRACT

The demand for natural peel-off masks in cosmetic care products has led to the exploration of botanical extracts such as Butterfly-pea flower (*Clitoria ternatea* Linn.). Herbal based peel-off masks prepared with extracts from the Butterfly-pea flower (*Clitoria ternatea* Linn.) provide a different concept in skincare which emphasizes the natural antioxidant properties of this floral plant. The flowers are flavonoid and anthocyanin rich and well known for their high antioxidant properties therefore they present anti-aging and anti-pigmentation properties. In this study, extracts of the Butterfly-pea flowers were prepared and used in the formulation of a peel-off mask to evaluate its antioxidant property. The extract was prepared by maceration extraction followed by concentration with an evaporating solvent in a hot air oven. The extracts were evaluated for antioxidant activity using the DPPH radical scavenging assay. The peel-off mask formulation was pH optimized and its spreadability tested for usability and stability as well. Significant results of antioxidants were demonstrated by the extract of butterfly pea flower. This peel-off mask is intended to forward the initial steps of aging prevention below this, by radical scavenging, enhancing skin moisture which is important for maintaining texture of skin and smoothness.

INTRODUCTION

Human skin is constantly directly exposed to the air, solar radiation, environmental pollutants, or other mechanical and chemical insults, which causes the generation of free radicals as well as reactive oxygen species (ROS) of our own metabolism. Ionizing radiation, extreme physical

and mental stress, alcohol consumption, poor diet, overeating, and pollution in the environment are some of the causes of extrinsic skin damage [1]. Among these is UV radiation, and repeated exposure to ultraviolet B (UV-B) is causing damage to DNA and the skin's function and structure, resulting in the skin aging process known as photoaging. Meanwhile, ultraviolet A

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(UV-A) has a longer wavelength and can penetrate deeper into dermic skin but is not causing damage to DNA. Photoaging is characterized by the appearance of a wrinkle due to collagen damage caused by the formation of ROS. Uncontrolled free radicals can also cause cellular tissue damage, resulting in symptoms such as redness, pigmentation, and an increased risk of cancer [2]. Therefore, the addition of antioxidants is necessary to address this insufficiency. Antioxidants are widely used to reduce and protect the skin from harmful ultraviolet radiation. Natural antioxidants from plant origin are well known to have fewer side effects than the manufactured ones [3,4]. Butterfly-pea's botanical name is *Clitoria ternatea* Linn. and belongs to the Fabaceae (Papilionaceae) family. It is known by different names as bluebell vine, blue pea, cordofan pea, Darwin pea, and many more, and is found in several countries worldwide, including Thailand, Malaysia, India, Kenya, Australia, Sri Lanka, and others [5]. *Clitoria ternatea* L. is rich in phenolic content and contains terpenoid compounds, anthocyanin, tannins, phenols, and flavonoids [6,7]. Due to these constituents, the butterfly pea (*Clitoria ternatea* L.) has potential as an anti-aging treatment for facial skin. The presence of phenolic compounds and flavonoids in *Clitoria ternatea* L. as antioxidants can ward off free radicals to inhibit oxidation, thereby slowing photooxidation from exposure to UV lights [8]. Studies have reported its other pharmacological activities, including nootropic, anticonvulsant, antidepressant, anti-anxiety, anti-stress, analgesic, anti-inflammatory, antihyperglycemic, antihyperlipidemic, antidiabetic, and platelet aggregation inhibitory actions [9, 10]. The peel-off face mask is one of the prominent forms of topical applications used to enhance the quality of the facial skin. The skin face mask has the virtue of being easily peeled off or removed as an elastic membrane [11]. Once it is completely dried, the

liquid film peels off from the face, leaving behind a thin, plasticized film without any residue. It effectively removes skin impurities and tightens, rejuvenates, and heals skin. The peel-off face mask is useful to treat the facial skin and can be used to minimize pores. Additionally, peel-off masks may provide slight moisturization while enhancing the occlusive effect, which promotes increased blood flow, activates skin cells, and facilitates impurity removal. In addition, it is also useful for soothing the muscles of the face and as a cleanser or freshener [12]. With these considerations, this study was aimed at developing and testing a peel-off face mask from butterfly-pea flowers.

Pharmacognosy of Butterfly-pea flower:

1. Plant profile:

Botanical Name: *Clitoria ternatea* Linn.

Common Name: Butterfly pea, blue pea and Cordofan pea

Synonyms: Asphota, Girikarni, Vishnukranta, Sankhapushpi, Sephanda, Sveta, Maha

Family: Papilionaceae

2. Taxonomic hierarchy:

Kingdom: Plantae

Phylum: Angiosperms

Order: Fabales

Family: Fabaceae

Genus: *Clitoria*

Species: *Clitoria Ternatea* Linn.^[13]

3. Other species of Clitoria:

Clitoria albiflora Mattei

Clitoria amazonum Benth

Clitoria Andrei Fantz.

Clitoria angustifolia Kunth [14]

MATERIAL AND METHOD:

Material:

The dried flowers of butterfly pea were purchased from the online market store, Flipkart E-commerce site, and were stored in airtight conditions till use. The *Clitoria ternatea* Linn blue flowers has been identified with the number MIT0227 at Mithibai College Of Arts, Chauhan Institute Of Science & Amrutben Jivanlal College Of Commerce And Economics. The techniques used for authentication are microscopy and morphology. Additional materials were used such as Polyvinyl alcohol (PVA), glycerine, hydroxypropyl methylcellulose (HPMC), gelatin, polyethylene glycol, citric acid, methanol, sulfuric acid and Levender oil.

METHODOLOGY:

1. Procedure for Extraction of butterfly-pea flower:

For the extraction of butterfly-pea flowers, it was dried at 40°C for 15-20 minutes to remove moisture from flowers and powdered using a mixer. The powder is then sifted using sieves to get fine powder for maximum extraction. According to a literature survey, alcoholic extract of butterfly-pea flower is prominent for antioxidant activity^[15,16]. Butterfly-pea flower extract is made by macerating the powdered drug in acidified methanol for 24 hours and then filtering it out using Whatman filter paper^[17,18]. Then the filtrate solvent is evaporated at 40°C in a hot air oven to get the extract^[19].

2. Phytochemical Screening of Butterfly-Pea Flower Extract:

The alcoholic extract of butterfly-pea (*Clitoria ternatea* L.) was tested for the presence of alkaloid, carbohydrate, terpenoid compounds, anthocyanin, glycoside, tannins, phenols, and flavonoids^[20,21].

3. Antioxidant Activity Test of Butterfly-Pea Flower Extract:

Antioxidant activity was tested using the DPPH (1,1-diphenyl-2-picrylhydrazyl) [method](#). As much as 10.0 mg of butterfly-pea flower extract stock solution was then put into a 10.0 ml volumetric flask, and methanol was added until the limit was reached and shaken homogeneously. Stocks of methanol extract were taken in amounts of 100, 200, 300, 400, and 500 µl. A DPPH solution of 3.0 ml and methanol up to the limit mark were added in a 5.0 ml volumetric flask. The solution was incubated for 30 min, and then the absorbance was measured at a wavelength of 516 nm using a UV-VIS spectrophotometer (LABINDIA Analytical UV 3200). The final concentrations of flower extract were 20, 40, 60, 80, and 100 ppm. The absorbance data was used to calculate the inhibition percentage of extract against DPPH free radical using the equation below:

$$\text{Percentage inhibition (\%)} = \frac{A_0 - A_1}{A_0} \times 100$$

Where, A_0 was the absorbance of the blank solution, while A_1 was the absorbance of the test solution. The IC₅₀ (Inhibition concentration 50%) was determined using the linear regression equation $y = bx + a$, where x is the concentration (µg/ml) and y is the percentage of inhibition^[22-24].

4. Formulation of peel-off gel mask base:

The base of the formulation was made with Polyvinyl alcohol (PVA) and with increasing concentrations of gelatin to form the best base for the peel-off mask with appropriate properties^[25].

The formulation table of peel-off mask base is listed below:

Table No. 01: Formulation table for peel-off base

Sr.no	Ingredients	B1	B2	B3
1.	Polyvinyl Alcohol (PVA)	14%	12%	10%
2.	Glycerine	3%	3%	3%
3.	Polyethylene glycol 400 (PEG 400)	1%	1%	1%
4.	Hydroxypropyl methylcellulose	0.5%	0.5%	0.5%
5.	Gelatin	4%	6%	8%
6.	Citric acid	0.1%	0.1%	0.1%
7.	Lavender oil	2-3 drops	2-3 drops	2-3 drops
8.	Water	QS	QS	QS

4.1 Physical evaluation of peel-off mask base:

The base of the formulation was evaluated by various organoleptic properties and physically by performing tests like pH, drying time, spreadability, and film-forming capacity [26]. And on the basis of test results, the most suitable base is selected for further trials.

5. Preparation of Peel-Off Mask:

All ingredients were weighed carefully using an analytical balance. Polyvinyl alcohol (PVA) and

HPMC dispersion was made at 70°C and cooled at room temperature till 40°C. Polyethylene glycol 400 (PEG 400) and glycerin were added to the dispersion when it attained room temperature. Meanwhile, dissolve gelatin with water by heating followed by cooling it at 40°C and then add it to the polymer dispersion along with citric acid with continuous stirring. After proper mixing of gelatin and citric acid, extract is added and stirred to get uniform mixing of extract. At the end, perfumery agents like lavender oil are added in a little quantity [27].

Table no. 2: Formulation Table of Butterfly-pea flower peel-off mask.

Sr.no	Ingredients	F1	F2	F3	F4
1.	Butterfly-pea flower extract	2%	5%	7.5%	10%
2.	Polyvinyl Alcohol (PVA)	12%	12%	12%	12%
3.	Glycerine	3%	3%	3%	3%
4.	Polyethylene glycol 400 (PEG)	1%	1%	1%	1%

5.	Hydroxypropyl methylcellulose	0.5%	0.5%	0.5%	0.5%
6.	Gelatin	6%	6%	6%	6%
7.	Citric acid	0.1%	0.1%	0.1%	0.1%
8.	Lavender oil	2-3 drops	2-3 drops	2-3 drops	2-3 drops
9.	Water	QS	QS	QS	QS

6. Physical evaluation of peel-off mask:

The physical evaluation involved were organoleptic, pH, drying and film forming, and spreadability. The organoleptic properties like colour, odour, texture and consistency was observed for the formulation. The pH was determined using pH paper available, drying time was performed by applying a sufficient amount of formulated base on a glass slide in a uniform layer and peeled off after drying. Drying time was determined by applying a Peel-off mask sample in a 4x4cm area and was dried at room temperature and time was noted. Film forming capability was checked by folding endurance of peel-off mask and it was performed by applying mask sample on skin in 3x3cm area and was rolled without breaking. It checks the resistance of the peel-off mask for breaking. Spreadability was determined using a glass slide on which 1gm of sample mask was placed and another slide was put on it with 5gm of weight for 5 minutes. Spreadability was determined using formula:

$$S = m \times l / t$$

Where,

S = Spreadability

l = length after spreading

m = weight of sample on slide

t = time [24-28].

RESULT AND DISCUSSION:

Result:

1.Extraction of butterfly-pea flower:

The dark blue colour of extract of *Clitoria ternatea* Linn were obtained with extractive value of 18.5% by using macerated extraction procedure.

2. Phytochemical Screening of Butterfly-pea flower Extract:

Table no. 3: Phytochemical Screening of Butterfly-pea flower Extract

Sr.no.	Chemical test	Compound	Observance	Result
1.	Wagner's test	Alkaloids	Formation of white precipitate	+
2.	Molisch's test	Carbohydrates	Red to violet ring at the interphase	+
3.	Alkaline reagent test	Flavonoids	Formation of yellow colour, becomes colourless in addition of dil. HCl	+
4.	Foam test	Saponins	No stable foam	-
5.	Ferric chloride test	Phenols	Formation of deep blue-green or black colour	+

6.	Precipitate test for tannins	Tannins	Red precipitate formation	+
7.	HCl test	Anthocyanin	Decolouration of pink colour.	+
8.	Salkowski's test	Terpenoids	Formation of a reddish-brown precipitate	+

3. Antioxidant Activity Test of Butterfly-pea flower Extract:

The results of antioxidant testing on Butterfly-pea flower extract proved that Butterfly-pea flower extract is 3.239 µg/ml.

4. Formulation and Preparation of peel-off gel mask base:

With the help of organoleptic properties and physical testing we found out that B2 base is appropriate for the formulation of peel-off mask for further trials.

4.1 Physical evaluation of peel-off gel mask base:

Table no. 4: Evaluation parameter data of base trials

Sr. no.	Parameters	B1	B2	B3
1.	pH	6	7	6.5
2.	Colour	Transparent	Transparent	Transparent-cloudy
3.	Odour	PVA like	PVA like	PVA like
4.	Texture	smooth and watery	smooth and viscous	not smooth
5.	Homogeneity	homogenous	homogenous	not homogenous
6.	Folding endurance	-	15 times	8 times
7.	Irritancy test	Non irritant	Non irritant	Non irritant
8.	Drying time (in mins)	6-7	10-15	15-25

5. Formulation and Preparation of Peel-off mask:

The organoleptic of peel-off gel mask preparation was homogenous violet-blue gel with the characteristic odour of lavender.

5.1. Physical evaluation of peel-off mask:

Table no.5: Evaluation parameter data of formulation trials

Parameters	F1	F2	F3	F4
pH	7	6.5	6.7	6
Colour	Bluegreen-violet	Violet	Violet-green	Violet-dark green
Odour	Lavender like	Lavender like	Lavender like	Lavender like
Texture	Smooth and viscous	Smooth and sticky	Smooth and gelly	Smooth and liquidy
Folding endurance	20 times	15 times	12 times	10 times
Homogeneity	Homogeneous	Homogeneous	Homogeneous	Homogeneous
Spreadability	6cm	5cm	6cm	5.6cm
Irritant test	Non-irritant	Non-irritant	Non-irritant	Non-irritant
Drying time (mins)	10-12	15-17	15-20	20-25

DISCUSSION:

1.Extraction of butterfly-pea flower:

Extraction of butterfly-pea flower powder was done by maceration method using acidified methanol. The method is chosen to avoid damage of active substances due to heating. Extra pure methanol was used to extract polar substances like flavonoid and anthocyanin. Active substances taken from butterfly-pea flower powder are flavonoids and anthocyanin which have an antioxidant effect. The extraction process will produce a liquid extract which is then concentrated by evaporating the solvent at 40-45 °C. The viscous extract obtained has characteristic odor and violet-blue in color. Extraction of 100 grams of butterfly-pea flower powder resulted in 18.5g (18.5%) viscous extract.

2. Phytochemical Screening of Butterfly-pea flower Extract:

Phytochemical screening tests include alkaloid, flavonoid, tannin, phenol, terpenoid and saponin tests. Butterfly-pea flower extract positively contains alkaloid, tannins, flavonoids and anthocyanin which is shown in Table no. 3

3.Antioxidant Activity Test of Butterfly-pea flower Extract:

Antioxidant activity test was Butterfly-pea flower extract using DPPH radical scavenging assay method. The principle of the DPPH radical scavenging assay method is that when the DPPH solution is mixed with a sample that has antioxidant activity, it causes a reduction form with the change of purple to yellow color. The results of antioxidant testing on butterfly-pea flower extract proved that the IC₅₀ of butterfly-pea flower extract is 3.239µg/ml. An antioxidant

agent which has high antioxidant activity will have a low IC₅₀ value. Butterfly-pea flower extract was able to inhibit 50% DPPH at concentration 3.239 µg/ml. In this study, Ascorbic acid was used as a reference standard. Since ascorbic acid is a

powerful antioxidant, its IC₅₀ value was higher. An IC₅₀ value of ≤ 50 ppm indicated a strong antioxidant whereas an IC₅₀ value of 50-100 indicated a moderate antioxidant property.

Table no. 6: DPPH radical scavenging assay of Butterfly-pea flower extract:

Sr.no	Conc. of sample (µg/ml)	Control	Test absorbance (nm)	Radical scavenging activity (RSA %)	IC ₅₀
1.	20	0.5907	0.5656	4.24	3.239
2.	40	0.5907	0.495	16.2	
3.	60	0.5907	0.3972	32.75	
4.	80	0.5907	0.3513	40.52	
5.	100	0.5907	0.2589	56.17	

Graph no. 01: DPPH radical scavenging assay of Butterfly-pea flower extract:

4. Formulation and Preparation of Peel-off mask base:

The peel-off gel mask base was formulated into three variance concentrations of PVA. The function of PVA is a film forming agent while the function of HPMC, propylene glycol, glycerin, gelatin, citric acid and distilled water is viscosity-increasing agent, humectant agent, soothing agent, thickening agent, and solvent, respectively. Different concentrations of PVA and gelatin were used to get the accurate drying time, spreadability, pH, etc. And on the basis that B2 was selected as the suitable base for the formulation of peel-off mask.

5. Formulation and Preparation of Peel-off mask:

Based on the calculation using IC₅₀ of Butterfly-pea flower extract, the concentration of Butterfly-pea flower extract used in the peel-off mask gel was 2% w/w. Variations of active extract concentrations in the formula were 2% (F1), 5% (F2), 7.5% (F3), 10% (F4) w/w. The various concentrations of active extract were aimed to get the concentration of active extract resulting in maximum antioxidant activity. F1 was chosen as the best formulation because it shows the proper organoleptic as well as physical test results

followed by least IC50 values indicating maximum-antioxidant activity.

6. Physical evaluation of peel-off mask:

The physical evaluation of peel-off mask was organoleptic, pH, drying, film forming, and spreadability which is shown in Table. no 5. Organoleptic test was carried out to see the physical appearance of the preparation by observing the color, odour, texture and consistency and homogeneity of the preparation. The texture of all formulations was the same. F1, F2, F3 and F4 were Violet - green in colour and characteristic odor of lavender oil added. Whereas B1, B2, and B3, which were control formula and base mask, had the appearance of clear white and PVA odor. Based on the tests performed, all of the formulas were a homogeneous preparation. The pH of mask preparations was approximately 7. The pH of the mask preparations was within the normal pH range of the skin (6-7). Formulas without extracts (B1, B2, and B3) were faster in dry time than the other three formulas containing extract. The drying test of the film showed that B2 dried faster than B1 and B3, this might be caused by the concentration of PVA in the formula. The fastest drying time for the film layer was B2 (10-15 minutes). Based on the data obtained only F1 which meets the requirement of the drying time of the peel-off gel mask (10-15 minutes). Based on the physical evaluation result showed that F1 was significantly better from F2, F3 and F4.

CONCLUSION:

The research has formulated and evaluated a peel-off facial mask using butterfly pea (*Clitoria ternatea* L.) flower extract which was carried out using maceration process with methanol as a solvent. The antioxidant activity of extract of *Clitoria ternatea* Linn showed IC50 value of 3.239 µg/ml . The formulation trials were conducted

with different active extract concentration such as F1, F2, F3 and F4. Based on organoleptic properties and physical evaluation , F1 were best among the others containing Butterfly-pea flower extract 2%, PVA 12%, HPMC 0.5%, polyethylene glycol 1%, glycerin 3%, gelatin 6%, Citric acid 0.1% and distilled water add 100% w/w was the best formula Overall, the study highlights the potential of butterfly pea flower as a valuable ingredient in natural skincare products.

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